

Conductivity, viscosity and volumetric behavior of molten hydrates of M^{3+} and M^{2+} ions^ψ

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Conductivity, density and viscosity of molten hydrated salts consisting of M^{3+} (Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+}) and M^{2+} (Ca^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) ions were measured over a wide composition range and at temperatures ranging between 273.2 to 363.2 K. Representative data for $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O + MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ is taken for the discussion purposes. A change in hydration envelope of the cations and the competition of anions for hydration are considered to be the main factors for deviations from the ideal behavior in volumetric properties-composition isotherms.

Temperature dependence of conductivity (Λ) and viscosity (η) was found to be non-Arrhenian; curvature in $\ln(\Lambda, \eta)$ vs T^{-1} curves indicate an increase in activation energy with decrease in temperature. The data were expressed using VTF equation, Free Volume Model (FVM) and Configurational Entropy Model (CEM) of liquid transport. The calculated values of zero mobility temperature, T_0 , exhibited a random variation with composition. The plot of $\ln(\Lambda, \eta)$ vs $(V - V_0)^{-1}$ were linear indicating the applicability of Doolittle equation. A parallelism between V_0 and $(V)_{T_0}$ vs composition indicate that free volume theory is applicable to describe the behavior of liquid transport in these system over the available temperature range. Composition dependence of the coefficients of VTF and Doolittle equations do not exhibit a systematic trend as expected from FVM and CEM. However, the standard deviations from the computer data fittings reveal that CEM formulations represent the data more closely to experimental values.

Applicability of environmental relaxation model (ERM) of liquid transport was also examined. Constancy of C_0 , the limiting activation energy, for conductivity and viscosity is attributed for small temperature range available in this study. The ϵ_0 values obtained in this study matches closely to the reported values for the similar systems. Though, ERM successfully predicts the temperature variations of transport properties, it is general observation that the parameters of ERM evaluated from a short range temperature data may not be useful to predict the behavior over wide range of temperatures.

Physicochemical investigations of electrolyte solutions were aimed to have a better understanding of ionic interactions in different solvents¹⁻¹⁹. Very dilute solutions of electrolytes have been extensively investigated by large of scientists since 1800 onwards. The active interest in the solution chemistry of electrolytes at low concentration region resulted into a primitive model of ions, interacting in a structure less dielectric medium, obeying Coulombs' law. On the other hand, anhydrous molten salts have also been extensively studied²⁰⁻⁴¹ with a view to their use as industrial solvents, electro-winning of metals, high energy-density storage batteries, nuclear reactors, disposal of wastes and vulcanology. Since working tem-

peratures were not very far from the melting points of the solids and all the ions were surrounded by opposite charge, a short-range quasi-lattice structure has been envisaged. Highly concentrated electrolyte solutions and molten hydrated salts⁹⁻¹⁹ form the intermediate concentration regions, where ion-dipole interactions predominate over ion-ion and dipole-dipole interactions, the nature of dipole (water molecules in aqueous medium) envelope is quite complex and a small variation in water content bring a large change in magnitude and nature of these interactions. The reported investigations¹⁹ in them is the testimony of this fact and a parabolic curve exhibited by conductivity-concentration curves, require more rigorous

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

understanding of ion-dipole interactions. However, the available data¹⁻¹⁹ on various physicochemical properties is small and there exists a serious data gap, as far as to develop a general theory for describing the behavior of these systems.

An understanding of highly concentrated aqueous electrolyte solutions and molten hydrates salts requires a more detailed knowledge of ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions for the large number of electrolytes and solvent media. As the solvent content decrease, ion-solvent interactions predominate over solvent-solvent interactions. At solvent-salt mol ratio (R) = 4-8, the solvent is just sufficient to form the first hydration envelope around the cations/anions, which may be extended to second, third and so on when more water is added, and there may be competition between ions and water molecules for the positions in first hydration envelope if the amount of water is decreased slightly. At this point, the properties of the system becomes molten salt like and bulk solvent structure no longer controls the behaviour of the solutions. Preliminary investigations of these solutions have revealed that decrease of water content is accompanied with a pronounced change in the spectra, bulk solution thermodynamics and structural and transport properties¹⁻¹⁹. For example, the enthalpy of vaporization showed a marked increase at $R = 4-8$; partial molal volumes exhibited a similar behaviour. Raman and IR spectra of LiNO_3 solutions showed the same at $R = 6$; near IR and PMR spectra of $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solutions exhibited a sharp increase in extinction of coefficients and also in chemical shift for the solution at $R = 8$. Temperature dependence of transport properties^{20-29,31-41} exhibited a marked departure from Arrhenian behavior, and conductivity-mole fraction isotherms¹⁹ exhibited maxima at 18% of electrolyte for M^+ salts, 4.5% of electrolytes for M^{2+} salts and at 2.1% electrolytes for M^{3+} salts. The behaviour of these type of systems has been explained considering the existence of weak-field cations of type $\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$; the water compete strongly with the ions to occupy positions as coordinated water in the hydration spheres of cations/anions, cations being small and having high charge density attract water more strongly than the anions.

The molten hydrated salts and highly concentrated aqueous electrolyte solutions have been considered promising materials for several technological developments. In search of alternative sources of energy, these materials have been considered for electrochemical and thermal energy storage²⁰⁻²⁹; in the former the cell reaction converts the chemical energy to electrical energy with high

efficiency and in later the enthalpy of fusion have been utilized without any sophisticated instrumentation. R & D in high energy density storage systems have been greatly facilitated by the availability of precise and meaningful data on various physical and transport properties, thermal parameters and electrochemical behaviour. The available literature on various aspects has been reviewed and critically evaluated by Janz and coworkers in the series of molten salt data.

Professor Harish Chandra Gaur¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and his coworkers¹¹ devoted more than 50 years on the studies of physicochemical particularly volumetric, surface properties, viscous and electrical transport, and optical and electrochemical behaviour of large number of molten and hydrated molten electrolytes, and highly concentrated electrolyte solutions. This paper presents the results of density, conductivity and viscosity measurements on hydrated molten electrolyte mixtures consisting of M^{3+} and M^{2+} ions being investigated during 1990-2004, and is dedicated to Professor Gaur on his 80th birthday.

Results and discussion

Density (ρ), conductivity (Λ) and viscosity (η) of aluminum nitrate decahydrate and ferric nitrate nonahydrate with the hydrated nitrates of calcium, cadmium, magnesium and zinc, and ferric chloride hexahydrate with magnesium chloride hexahydrate mixtures were measured at temperatures ranging between 273.2 to 363.2 K, over the entire concentration range.

Data have been expressed in terms of linear or polynomial equations. The empirical parameters were calculated by the method of least square fitting using IBM data processing system. The density, conductivity and viscosity of individual salts are in good agreement (within $\pm 0.1\%$) with those reported earlier.

Equivalent volumes (V_e) vs equivalent fraction (X) isotherms for systems consisting of Mg^{2+} ions were found non-linear indicating that systems were not volumetrically ideal; the partial equivalent volumes being a non-linear function of composition. The curvature in ρ vs X and V_e vs X plots indicated a decrease in packing density on addition of Mg^{2+} ions. Considering both the cations to be hydrated, addition of $\text{Mg}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ ($r = 3.44 \text{ \AA}$) would replace $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ ($r = 3.42 \text{ \AA}$) in per unit volume. Since both the cations are of the same size, the density and volume data indicate a change in the ion-water interactions thereby affecting the shape and size of hydration envelope of cations.

A non-linear increase in κ is obtained when plotted

against mol fraction (X) of $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$. In terms of anion polarization model, the addition of $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ would set the Cl^- ions in a local environment such that the first coordination cell would contain $Fe(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ and $Mg(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ ions. Because of the difference in cationic potential for $Fe(H_2O)_6^{3+} = 0.88$ and $Mg(H_2O)_6^{2+} = 0.58$ of the two, Cl^- ions would be subjected to oppositely directed electric fields of different intensity. This would result in the polarization of the electron cloud of Cl^- ions in the direction of $Fe(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ thus enhancing the $Fe(H_2O)_6^{3+}-Cl^-$ ion interactions and weakening the attractive forces between $Mg(H_2O)_6^{2+}-Cl^-$ ions. The preferential attachment of Cl^- to Fe^{3+} ions would increase the mobility of $Mg(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ ions. Viscosity-composition isotherms were non-linear and $\log \Phi$ vs X isotherms did not obey Kendall equation.

The Arrhenius plot of equivalent conductivity (Λ) and fluidity (Φ) were curved in a direction that decreasing temperature increases the apparent activation energy. The

ionic movement or flow of liquid did not cease at $0^\circ K$ but a higher temperature. The $(\Lambda, \Phi) - T$ data could be explained using Vogel-Tammann-Fulcher³¹ equation,

$$\Lambda, \Phi = A1 \exp \left(-\frac{B1}{T - T_0} \right) \quad (2)$$

and the equations based on free volume model³³ (FVM),

$$\Lambda, \Phi = A2 T^{-1/2} \exp \left(-\frac{B2}{T - T_0} \right) \quad (3)$$

and configurational entropy model³⁴ (CEM),

$$\Lambda, \Phi = A3 T^{-1/2} \exp \left(-\frac{B3}{T \ln T / T_0} \right) \quad (4)$$

of liquid transport. The empirical constants A 's, B 's and the zero mobility temperature T_0 for conductivity and fluidity data have been included in Table 1. Reliability of computer evaluation of these parameters is supported by the linearity of the plots of $\ln (\Lambda, \Phi)$ vs $(T - T_0)^{-1}$,

Table 1. Parameters of eq. (2), FVM and CEM for conductivity and fluidity data of $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O + MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ system

Mole fraction	0.0000	0.1002	0.2082	0.3033	0.3934	0.5306	0.6056	
→								
Parameters ↓								
			$\Lambda = A1 \exp \left(-\frac{B1}{T - T_0} \right)$					
A1	331.5	475.7	736.9	847.3	979.5	995.9	987.3	
B1	749.98	800.02	799.96	799.96	799.96	799.94	799.96	
T_0	188.39	179.99	182.44	180.60	179.95	177.86	176.76	
SE	0.03	0.07	0.08	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.07	
			$B1 = 750.0$					
A1	479.1	716.9	987.7	1217.2	1453.9	1619.4	1695.1	
T_0	194.89	194.83	194.88	194.86	194.86	194.84	194.82	
SE	0.18	0.30	0.24	0.28	0.29	0.33	0.36	
			$\Lambda = A2 T^{-1/2} \exp \left(-\frac{B2}{T - T_0} \right)$					
A2	6386.9	19555.3	8156.7	9442.7	9339.4	7570.4	9180.0	
B2	748.02	1001.09	661.59	660.13	623.58	569.17	613.15	
T_0	190.15	167.42	195.21	193.77	196.25	199.40	194.53	
SE	0.03	0.07	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.05	
			$B2 = 750.0$					
A2	8544.1	12746.4	17518.2	21698.5	25900.1	28882.8	30242.4	
T_0	194.92	194.86	194.90	194.86	194.88	194.86	194.84	
SE	0.14	0.26	0.19	0.23	0.25	0.29	0.32	

Table-1 (contd.)

$\Lambda = A3 T^{-1/2} \exp \left(-\frac{B3}{T \ln T / T_0} \right)$							
A3	3160.6	8378.3	4307.0	5029.1	5715.3	4332.9	5098.5
B3	891.99	1293.15	775.95	778.45	730.12	659.82	721.16
T ₀	189.37	157.71	190.20	188.57	191.31	194.91	189.39
SE	0.02	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.05
B3 = 750.0							
A3	2368.0	3519.2	4820.8	6051.1	7208.4	8048.9	8804.3
T ₀	194.97	194.91	194.95	194.97	194.43	194.91	194.89
SE	0.05	0.26	0.19	0.23	0.25	0.29	0.32
$\Phi = A1 \exp \left(-\frac{B1}{T - T_0} \right)$							
A1	36.2	45.4	50.2	50.6	55.6	37.8	26.3
B1	750.05	749.98	749.99	149.99	149.98	749.97	749.98
T ₀	190.87	193.91	193.53	193.47	194.36	191.82	190.92
SE	0.09	0.06	0.04	0.95	0.07	0.06	0.11
B1 = 750.0							
A1	44.1	49.4	53.8	54.5	56.0	44.0	32.0
T ₀	194.97	194.99	194.99	194.99	195.00	194.98	194.98
SE	0.013	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.13
$\Phi = A2 T^{-1/2} \exp \left(-\frac{B2}{T - T_0} \right)$							
A2	67914.2	332.2	377.6	248.9	489.8	241.8	271.5
B2	2332.36	527.37	523.19	805.77	565.27	490.48	594.23
T ₀	199.02	213.79	215.61	191.04	212.07	216.95	206.19
SE	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.06	0.02	0.11
B2 = 750.0							
A2	794.6	884.3	971.7	982.4	1008.3	793.1	576.3
T ₀	194.99	195.00	195.00	195.00	195.01	194.99	194.99
SE	0.11	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.11
$\Phi = A3 T^{-1/2} \exp \left(-\frac{B3}{T \ln T / T_0} \right)$							
A3	191.7	195.6	226.3	611.8	280.8	148.3	153.8
B3	592.87	596.62	599.25	979.74	643.72	553.43	688.60
T ₀	168.25	210.26	211.75	184.03	208.19	213.44	201.50
SE	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.06	0.02	0.10
B3 = 750.0							
A3	226.33	248.89	277.83	279.97	287.15	226.33	164.30
T ₀	195.01	195.04	195.02	195.03	195.04	195.02	195.01
SE	0.11	0.10	0.09	0.11	0.14	0.07	0.11

SE - standard error.

$\ln(\Lambda, \Phi) T^{1/2}$ vs $(T - T_0)^{-1}$ and $\ln(\Lambda, \Phi) T^{1/2}$ vs $(T/T_0)^{-1}$. The plots reveal that $T^{-1/2}$ terms in FVM and CET equations has a negligible effect on linearity. The standard errors indicate that CEM fits the data better.

Composition variation of pre-exponential term, $A_{(\Lambda, \Phi)}$ did not exhibit a systematic variation. Turnbull model³³ suggested that a direct dependence of $A_{(\Lambda, \Phi)}$, on particle size and an inverse dependence on the square root of particle mass. The pre-exponential coefficient has been shown to be insensitive to particle radii for ionic molten system. Thus, the addition of M^{2+} to M^{3+} should result in a systematic increase in $A_{(\Lambda, \Phi)}$. A random variation of $A_{(\Lambda, \Phi)}$ with composition require a more appropriate formulation to describe it. However, when $B_{(\Lambda, \Phi)}$ was kept constant, a systematic increase in $A_{(\Lambda, \Phi)}$ was observed (Table 1). $B1$ is almost constant while $B2$ and $B3$ exhibit a random variation with composition. FVM³³ relates :

$$B_{(\Lambda, \Phi)} = \frac{\gamma V^*}{\alpha V_m} \quad (5)$$

where α is the mean expansion coefficient of the melt over the temperature range T to T_0 and γ , a correction factor for overlapping free volume in the calculation of the probability of occurrence of a critical void (V^*) and V_m the mean molecular volume per particle. For random distribution of free volume γ must have a value $1/2 < \gamma < 1$. The value of $\gamma V^*/V_m$ calculated from B 's for the system ranged from 0.50 to 0.97, whereas 0.5 to 1.0 is expected from the theory depending on the value of γ . It appeared, therefore, that in these systems the random distribution of free volume take place. However, several workers have reported a non-random distribution of free volume in ionic melts. The large values of expansion coefficients of these mixtures and the random distribution of free volume suggest that free volume available for various ions was in large quantity and voids of critical sizes are generated. The cation free volume fraction and anion free volume fraction could not be visualized independently, which unbalance the negative exponential distribution of free volume.

The ideal glass transition temperature (T_0) exhibited a random variation with the addition of $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$. It has been recognized that T_0 is a useful parameter to measure the interaction energy between the bulk species of the system. In molten hydrated salts the total interaction energy would be contributed by ion-ion, ion-water and water-water interactions; that due to ion-water interactions will predominate. Although addition of M^{2+} to M^{3+}

would decrease the Coulombic energy of the system, the examination of T_0 reveal that total cohesive energy of the system varied randomly. Preferential hydration of cations along with hydration of anions suggested the existence of $Mg(H_2O)_x^{2+}$, $Fe(H_2O)_y^{3+}$, $Cl(H_2O)_z^-$ ions; a non-systematic variation in the concentration of these ions may not be ruled out^{13,14,28,29}. Several types of interactions could be visualized. Fe^{3+} may de-coordinate water molecules from Mg^{2+} ions; polarization of water dipoles towards Fe^{3+} ions and anionic hydration. The variation of these interactions in a non-systematic manner is not surprising.

The Λ, Φ vs $(V - V_0)^{-1}$ plots tend to be non-linear indicating the inability of the Hildebrand equation to explain the present data. The data was least square fitted into Doolittle equation.

$$\Lambda, \Phi = A4 \exp \left(-\frac{B4}{V - V_0} \right) \quad (6)$$

Parameters of eq. (6) were evaluated using computer. The linearity of $\ln A_{(\Lambda, \Phi)} (V - V_0)^{-1}$ plots exhibited the applicability of the equation. V_0 was characterized as intrinsic or closed packed volume of the system. No systematic variation in $A4$ and $B4$ with composition was seen in this study. The intrinsic volumes V_0 for a particular composition, from $\Lambda - T$ and $\Phi - T$ fittings were in good agreement. V_0 may be considered as the volume of the system at T_0 . The equivalent volumes evaluated from V_0 vs T fittings at T_0 and V_0 are plotted against X ; a parallelism between the two established the usefulness of Doolittle equation to describe the transport data.

The applicability of environmental relaxation model⁴¹ (ERM) to and data has also been examined. The $\Lambda - T$ and $\Phi - T$ data was processed in,

$$\Lambda, \Phi = \ln AG_\infty + \frac{E}{RT} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{C_0}{RT} \left\{ \frac{1}{1 - \epsilon_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_0} \right)^4} \right\}^{3/2} \quad (7)$$

using IBM 360/44 data processing system and its parameters AG_∞ , E , C_0 and T_0 were evaluated (Table 2). Since T_0 is the temperature at which the magnitude of transport properties reduces to zero, it should be constant for a particular chemical system and independent of transport

process. The T_0 evaluated using FVM, CEM or ERM should thus be the same. The parameters of the eq. (7) were evaluated by iteration method keeping T_0 constant and adopting its value from FVM.

Variation of the parameters of ERM with composition were also examined. The parameter $\ln (AG_\infty)$, is the product of frequency factor of Eyring rate equation and instantaneous shear modulus. A non-systematic variation in $\ln (AG_\infty)$ was obtained from $\Lambda - T$ and $\Phi - T$ fittings of data. Since the frequency factor A obtained from VTF exhibited a similar variation, it could be concluded that the instantaneous shear modulus of these systems remained almost constant. E is the average energy around which the Gaussian distribution of activation energy takes place. Variation of E exhibited a reverse trend than that of ($\ln AG_\infty$). While in some composition E_Λ was greater than E_Φ reverse order was observed in other compositions. This could be attributed to the different temperature range available for conductivity and viscosity measurements.

The parameter C_0 has been found constant for both the conductivity and fluidity. In molten anhydrous salts it was concluded from dielectric relaxation that relaxing species for conductivity were the cations while anions were relaxing species for viscous flow. The constancy of C_0 over the whole concentration region thus revealed that activation energy of these mixtures converges to the same point for the low temperatures. However, the dif-

ferent relaxing species for different transport processes would result different structural interaction which predict that,

$$C_{0,\Lambda} = \frac{C_0}{q^3} \quad (8)$$

where q is a constant and its value for molten anhydrous salts was found to be 1.18 while for present systems it is unity. This indicates that low temperature limit of activation energy for conduction and flow processes must be same. This, however, could not be taken true. The constancy of C_0 in present study might be due to a small temperature range available. Value of low temperature activation energy will be more acceptable if obtained from extended low temperature region data. ϵ_0 , which relates the size of microstructure to range of interactions was found almost constant for the system and its value was found to be 22 ± 5 . For concentrated solutions on which work is in progress in this laboratory, the value of ϵ_0 ranges between 5–30. Similar investigations in molten salt systems^{37–41} have reported a value of 5–50. It has been considered that in non-Arrhenius region the size of microstructure is of the same order as the range of structural interactions^{37–41}. For a particular composition, range of interaction will be same and size of microstructure data will provide a limiting value of ϵ_0 which will be characteristic of chemical system. The ratio of $\epsilon_{0,\Lambda}$ and

Table 2. Parameters of eq. (7) for conductivity and fluidity data of $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system

Mol fraction (X)	Temp. range (T, K)	AG_∞	$-E$	$-C_0$	ϵ_0	SE
$\Lambda - T$ data						
0.000	273–363	276478.96	33.045	831.40	26.723	0.08
0.100	273–363	426769.78	33.403	831.40	31.791	0.10
0.208	273–363	312606.35	31.513	831.40	26.527	0.11
0.303	273–363	253877.26	30.363	831.40	26.768	0.08
0.393	273–363	229300.81	29.600	831.40	26.422	0.09
0.531	273–363	156448.16	28.281	831.40	26.371	0.09
0.606	273–363	174828.36	28.529	831.40	27.310	0.10
$\phi - T$ data						
0.100	273–363	10807.55	29.854	831.40	19.507	0.04
0.208	273–363	7327.21	28.369	831.40	17.474	0.03
0.303	273–363	28424.31	32.315	831.40	20.669	0.05
0.393	273–363	16739.89	30.556	831.40	18.745	0.13
0.531	273–363	4527.84	27.685	831.40	18.186	0.05
0.606	273–363	5390.27	29.175	831.40	19.726	0.10

SE – standard error.

$\epsilon_{\Lambda, \Phi}$ was also found to be unity while ERM suggest.

$$\epsilon_{0, \Lambda} = \frac{\epsilon_{0, \Phi}}{q^3}$$

The low value of q may be considered to arise due to a small temperature range available for the study.

Experimental

All the salts in this study were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade purity; water content (R) of the salts, determined by volumetric titrations³⁰ using EDTA, were found within ± 0.01 of the stoichiometric value. Mixtures of varying compositions were prepared individually by mixing calculated amounts of the components, fusing them in inert atmosphere in a stoppered vessel, filtering and maturing at 5–10° above the melting point for 3 h.

The densimeter was essentially of the type used by Husband and McAuley⁴², modified to accommodate a wide range of temperatures. Densimeters were calibrated⁴³ using triple distilled water and vacuum distilled mercury at several temperatures between fluidicial points. A Beckmann conductivity bridge (Model RC-18A) based on Wein's bridge principle, provided with a CRT null detector and Wagner ground and operating at an a.c. frequency of 1 kHz was used to measure the molten salts resistances. A decade capacitance (C_p) box was connected in parallel with the decade resistance box (R_p) in the measuring arm of the bridge and the resistances in the ratio arms were matched. Considering the cell as a series combination of a resistance (R_s) and a capacitance (C_s), at balance point on has :

$$R_s = R_p / [1 + (2\pi f C_p R_p)^2] \quad (1)$$

where f is the frequency of a.c. signal in Hz. A dip capillary type conductivity cell was used to measure the conductivity of molten hydrated salts. The cell was calibrated^{43,44} using 1.0 and 0.1 molal KCl solutions. Viscosity was measured using a three limb UCF type viscometer, calibrated⁴³ using 20% and 40% sucrose solutions and 98% glycerol.

Concluding remarks :

Additivity of volumes is not followed by these systems, which may be explained in terms of marked changes in ion-water interaction. Non-Arrhenian temperature dependence of transport properties [conductivity (Λ) and viscosity (η)] is an indicative of near glassy-state of the system. Environmental relaxation model (ERM) adequately

explains the transport behaviour of these ionic liquids, the available short temperature range data in these system limit the applicability of evaluated parameters, which may not be acceptable for explaining the behaviour over the entire range of concentration and temperature. Non-Arrhenius behavior of transport properties could be better explained by Configurational Entropy Model.

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